

**TRADUIRE LE LEXIQUE CHRÉTIEN-ORTHODOXE.
QUELQUES ÉQUIVALENCES RITUELLES, LITURGIQUES ET SPIRITUELLES /
TRANSLATING THE CHRISTIAN-ORTHODOX LEXICON.
SOME RITUAL, LITURGICAL AND SPIRITUAL EQUIVALENTS**

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We propose a translational analysis of some ritual, liturgical and spiritual equivalents for certain Romanian and French words, encountered in texts of Orthodox theology and spirituality submitted for translation between the two Romance languages. We are working on a corpus of specialized translations of such texts, between Romanian and French, in both directions of the translational act, which we have carried out ourselves from a number of theologian authors who are consecrated in both cultures. Given the socio-religious particularities of these two cultures, Romanian and French, the confessional equivalences proposed for words with Orthodox specificities are subject to critical evaluation of the prescriptive norms of the linguistic imaginary constructed by the readers of these versions, coupled with a cultural imaginary. We will analyze several equivalences that must be used to “properly” translate the Orthodox-Christian lexicon, which we have classified as ritual, liturgical and spiritual.